

Modeling a stochastic multi-objective supplier quota allocation problem with price-dependent ordering

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Abstract

One of the interesting subjects in supply chain management is supply management, which generally relates to the activities regarding suppliers such as empowerment, evaluation, partnerships and so on. A major objective of supplier evaluation involves buyers determining the optimal quota allocated to each supplier when placing an order. In this paper, we propose a multi-objective model in which purchasing cost, rejected units, and late delivered units are minimized, while the obtained total score from the supplier evaluation process is maximized. We assume that the buyer obtains multiple products from a number of predetermined suppliers. The buyer faces a stochastic demand with a probability distribution of Poisson regarding each product type. A major assumption is that the supplier prices are linearly dependent on the order size of each product. Since demand is stochastic, the buyer may incur holding and stockout costs in addition to the regular purchasing cost. We use the well-known L-1 metric method to solve the supplier evaluation problem by utilizing two meta-heuristic algorithms to solve the corresponding mathematical problems.

Keywords: Supplier selection, Quota allocation, Stochastic demand, Inventory, Price-dependent demand, Meta-heuristic.